

Upscaling and replication guide for a multi-functional market model

Why adapt a multi-functional market model?

Markets have historically served as important nodes of trade and social interaction, contributing to quality of life for urban dwellers. However, with the proliferation of alternative retail options beginning in the mid-20th century - shopping malls, convenience stores, and e-commerce platforms - their former role diminished. Social activities and needs once fulfilled in the marketplace also found other outlets, with people increasingly seeking them in the private realm or other public venues and establishments.

In recent years, in line with broader urban sustainability initiatives and the UN New Urban Agenda, markets are increasingly being recognised for their untapped potential for bolstering well-being in cities. Key to this is taking their core commerce and social functions and expanding upon them by transforming venues into vibrant social hubs that combine leisure, education, cultural events, and environmentally oriented initiatives.

At its core, the multifunctional model integrates flexible and accessible infrastructure with a range of necessary and optional functions, offering diverse public avenues for meaningful engagement and fulfilment of various needs in one place.

Community engagement

Central to the idea of multi-functionality is that markets go beyond being just spaces of retail and incidental socialisation, serving instead as hubs that actively promote cultural events, community gatherings, workshops, and performances that engage diverse audiences.

Guided by public space quality and IHW principles, markets can support socialisation and visitor self-initiated activities by serving as "third places", welcoming neutral gathering grounds where people can foster relationships outside of work and domestic life.

More than just providing leisure and entertainment opportunities, markets can also serve as nodes for disseminating knowledge, practices, as well as foster inclusivity through educational initiatives.

Key principles:

- **Co-ownership and co-governance of programming** is essential to ensure events reflect local interests and that communities play an active role in shaping the market's evolving identity.
- **Regular free events** help foster community engagement and support the inclusion of diverse groups.
- **Socialisation is bolstered by adopting a "public living room" management approach for seating areas** - visitors can spend extended periods in these areas without feeling obliged to make purchases, as well as have a high degree of freedom to reconfigure seating arrangements to accommodate diverse other activities, including leisure, socialising, work, or play.

Infrastructure

Physical infrastructure shapes how multi-functional markets function as inclusive public spaces. The core principle is that the market accommodates diverse users – from elderly shoppers to families with young children, to people with mobility and health challenges. Comfort, weather protection, waste reduction, safety, accessibility, and aesthetic appeal are all essential aspects that shape inclusive and attractive markets.

The second core characteristic is adaptability – multiple facilities supporting different activities and flexible spaces allow the market to host events either simultaneously or at different times, transforming the venue to serve a variety of purposes.

Key principles:

- **Adaptable, event/public gathering spaces** are an efficient means for maximising the variety of use of limited space by alternating their functions.
- **Accessibility features and ergonomic and anthropometric design principles** enable the use of the venue by diverse publics.
- **Dedicated waste reduction facilities** not only foster a cleaner, safer environment, but also reduce waste volumes and management costs.

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The co-deployment and co-management approach

To ensure that multi-functional solutions are relevant and align with community preferences and needs, it is crucial to co-design them with multiple stakeholder groups using balanced top-down and bottom-up approaches.

Structured implementation hinges on establishing a skilled steering group responsible for stakeholder onboarding and coordination, data gathering and evaluation, and solution proposal drafting, refinement, and implementation.

At the outset, the core team should map stakeholders affected by the development, and contact target group representatives to form an advisory board, including both long term and situational members who assist with solution refinement.

The wider community – neighbourhood residents and intervention target groups (seniors, students, tourists, families, vulnerable populations) – should be regularly consulted using data gathering approaches (online and on-site) to assess intervention relevance.

Key lessons for other cities:

- IN-HUB work must be grounded in the city's wellbeing context, population needs, and development plans and policies.
- It is crucial to build upon existing development projects and initiatives to maximise the IN-HUB's relevance and impact through strategic synergies.
- The IN-HUB needs to maintain an open structure designed to stimulate co-creation, requiring continuous mobilisation, facilitation, monitoring, and evaluation to ensure effectiveness.
- Improving health and wellbeing depends on expanding the IN-HUB through purposeful networking with stakeholders.
- Successful co-design and deployment of sustainable health and wellbeing solutions requires skilful IN-HUB management. It falls upon the steering group to assess feasibility and implement solutions, often finding compromises between divergent stakeholder opinions.
- Collaboration must be tailored iteratively, adapting procedures based on changing circumstances and capacities of involved parties. Respecting professional commitments of IN-HUB members is a key consideration.

STEP 1	Identify community needs, interests, and preferences through surveys, interviews, or forums.
STEP 2	Gather feedback on potential activities via in-person and online sessions.
STEP 3	Develop proposals outlining objectives, audience, format, resources, and expected outcomes.
STEP 4	Refine proposals based on community input.
STEP 5	Brainstorm, prioritise activities, develop action plans, and assign responsibilities collaboratively.
STEP 7	Finalise detailed plans with community members.
STEP 8	Execute activities according to agreed timelines and plans.
STEP 9	Review outcomes, identify lessons learned, and inform future initiatives.

Infrastructure provides affordances for meaningful use of the market by diverse stakeholders

Iterative design loop for ongoing infrastructure and community engagement activity development

Maintaining and developing a multi-functional market that caters to diverse public needs requires ongoing monitoring and active community involvement.

The iterative design loop illustrates the logic behind responsive refinement: infrastructure provides users with a range of affordances for meaningful use, and as people engage with the market's premises, amenities, and features, behavioral patterns begin to emerge.

By monitoring these patterns and gathering feedback, planners can identify which aspects of the market are most valued, which areas require improvement, and how different user groups interact with the space. This insight then guides iterative adjustments to infrastructure, programming, and services, ensuring the market remains responsive, inclusive, and relevant to the community it serves.

Key lessons for other cities:

- **It is not possible to account for everything at the outset.** Even with careful planning and co-designing with community members and experts, unforeseen needs and circumstances will emerge as people begin to inhabit the venue. Therefore, monitoring and co-designing should be conducted regularly.
- **Design can raise the probability of certain behaviours occurring, but not determine them.** It is crucial to observe and reflect on which solutions work, which do not, and why. Special attention needs to be devoted to user stress points. Combining surveys, observations, and focus groups is key to uncovering motivations behind use patterns.
- **Major infrastructure solutions should be implemented with long-term considerations in mind.** Planning structural changes that allow for flexible adaptation is essential to respond to evolving conditions, including emerging user needs, the impacts of climate change, and the effective management of capacity in the face of increasing visitor numbers.

Market diversity and tailored replication

At the outset of planning replication activities, it is crucial to acknowledge the complexity of marketplaces as hybrid public and commercial spaces.

The diversity of market formats (temporary/permanent, open-air/covered/indoor, thematic focus), governance arrangements, as well as pursued concepts are all factors that influence how directly specific solutions can be replicated.

Therefore, a context-sensitive approach – understanding each venue’s unique circumstances, capacities, and aims – is paramount before tailoring infrastructure or community engagement solutions for replication in other markets.

Building a collaboration network with other market stakeholders and starting with soft replication activities – such as on-site demonstrations, knowledge sharing, and experience exchange events – is the first step in raising awareness of multi-functional solutions and encouraging other stakeholders to consider how to adapt them for their own venues.

The IN-HUB co-deployment and co-management approach can be adapted to foster dialogue between diverse marketplace actors and across multiple levels of governance, thus ensuring that each market’s situation is understood with input from multiple perspectives.

Key lessons for other cities:

- Stakeholder mapping, condition pre-assessments, and focus group discussions are essential methods during the initial phase.
- When contacting other market stakeholders for collaboration or joint events, it is beneficial to distribute an online survey in advance. This helps collect key information about each venue, including market format, concept, operational characteristics, and open-ended inputs on needs and expectations.
- Experience exchange events provide an effective platform for bringing together different stakeholder groups across multiple levels of governance that may not normally have opportunities to interact. These events support dialogue, mutual learning, and the identification of concrete needs.
- Skilled moderation by event organisers is crucial to ensure balanced participation, inclusive discussion, and productive outcomes for all stakeholders.

REPLICATION GUIDE "STEP - BY - STEP"

KEY ELEMENTS

RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS

PRECONDITIONS, BARRIERS AND CHALLENGES

SUSTAINABILITY AND IMPACT

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Replicable elements

Low investment, short term replicable elements

Accessibility improvements

- Implement universal design principles for all user groups
- Ensure pedestrian-friendly layouts and public seating

Public space enhancements

- Prioritise greenery, seating, and community gathering areas
- Designate non-commercial areas for social interaction and events

Community engagement and cultural programming

- Host concerts, seasonal festivals, workshops, or masterclasses
- Organise thematic or niche market days (e.g., eco-weekends, craft Saturdays)

Support for local producers and short supply chains

- Curate vendors to highlight small farmers, artisans, and urban food makers
- Promote eco-friendly and sustainable products

Waste reduction measures

- Introduce waste sorting, reusable packaging, and eco-friendly vendor rules
- Run small-scale initiatives like re-use events, composting, or urban gardening

Food and gastronomy activation

- Create low-cost café areas, street-food corners, or ready-to-eat counters
- Encourage communal dining or co-creation kitchens

Digital communication practices

- Maintain active social media accounts and clear visual branding
- Promote vendors and events online to engage the community

Market aesthetics and visitor comfort (incremental improvements)

- Improve layout, lighting, cleanliness, and signage
- Add cosy corners or decorative elements without full-scale renovation

Event curating capacity building

- Organisational procedures, skills and knowledge capacity building, finance planning, and stakeholder engagement approaches

High investment, long term replicable elements

Major renovations to improve accessibility

- Install permanent lifts, ramps, and barrier-free circulation, widened corridors and doorways, and accessible sanitary facilities

Adaptable multi-functional spaces

- Purposefully design and create indoor and outdoor areas for flexible use across commercial, social, cultural, and educational activities
- Procure different event type equipment (sound systems, lighting, monitors, etc.) for easy activation by partners and community groups

Permanent community facilities

- Install equipped community kitchens and learning spaces that enable long-term programming

Integrated circular economy infrastructure

- Construct on-site waste sorting and reduction facilities embedded into daily operations, supported by education and dedicated staff capacity

Consumption-independent public areas

- "Public living room" areas not tied to vendors, allowing extended, flexible, non-commercial use

Key lessons for other cities:

- **High investment, long term solutions require alignment between municipal and market planning at early stages.** Changes must complement the supporting infrastructure on a neighbourhood level
- **Both market and municipal stakeholders should be proactive about communicating with one another.** Stakeholder discussions highlighted the lack of communication and engagement as key barriers for solution implementation

Iterative event life cycle for community-based markets

Replication Logic

- Inputs and activities are adaptable to local contexts
- Outputs are measurable and comparable
- Outcomes and impact align with public policy
- Iteration ensures continuous improvement over time

Applicability

- This model can be replicated by:
- Local and regional markets
 - Municipalities and public authorities
 - Cultural, food, and placemaking organisations

Scale	Local > Regional > National > EU level					
Stakeholders	Policy makers & governmental bodies	Market actors	NGOs, Associations	Education / cultural organisations	Research organisations	Wider public
Contribution	Improve development planning documents, facilitate regulatory frameworks for markets, promote stakeholder cooperation with local governments and community organisations	Adapt multi-functional market principles, develop and share good practices, communicate practical requirements	Facilitate community engagement, inclusion, and local capacity building	Foster food literacy and intergenerational participation via events	Contribute evidence, impact evaluation, innovation tools, dissemination via events	Contribute feedback, generate word-of-mouth promotion, community engagement
Engagement strategies	Evidence based policy briefs aligned with EU objectives, data and success stories of measurable impact	Collaboration events, conferences, showcase events, joint knowledge sharing platform	Partnership agreements, joint campaigns, workshops, user advisory board involvement	Educational programs, exhibitions, student engagement programs	Research project partnerships, thematic event participation	Public campaigns, co-creation activities, events showcasing multi-functional format

Building a market network and strengthening capacity to adopt multi-functional solutions at a larger scale

Markets vary significantly in their capacity to implement multifunctional solutions, depending on governance arrangements, available resources, and the level of support provided by municipal structures. As a result, many community-driven market initiatives struggle to sustain momentum and discontinue without adequate support mechanisms.

Realising the multifunctional potential of markets at scale therefore requires a shift from isolated initiatives to a coordinated, structural approach. This entails the establishment of a unified platform and formal association of market stakeholders, led by an experienced steering group.

Such an association would provide markets with a unified voice and enhanced capacity to coordinate advocacy efforts, engage with institutions, influence policy, secure funding, and facilitate cross-sector partnerships. Crucially, it would enable the strategic alignment between markets.

Central to this approach is the development of a broad, multi-level stakeholder collaboration network - spanning local, regional, national, and EU levels - to promote and embed the multifunctional market model. This networked structure would support the scaling of impact, inform policy development, and lay the groundwork for long-term sustainability through dedicated policies and national funding programmes.

Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring focus / Indicators	Methods	Outputs
<p>Reach Community impact</p> <p>Sustainability</p>	<p>Surveys of participants, vendors, community partners</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insights on satisfaction levels, Usage patterns, Perceived impacts on well-being
<p>Quantitative indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of participants Attendance figures Vendor participation rates Revenue diversification ratios 	<p>Semi-structured interviews with managers, municipal and long-term partners</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reveal operational challenges, Adaptation strategies, Community transformation stories
<p>Qualitative & social impact indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community ownership Partnership strength Integration of commercial and social activities Local food access Social cohesion Health behaviour change Policy influence 	<p>Participant observation protocols</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation of actual versus intended use patterns, Quality of social interactions, Integration of hub functions
	<p>Theory of change + Participatory evaluation methods</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A structured framework linking outcomes to long-term impacts, with community-defined success metrics, enabling iterative learning and adaptation

Tracking the upscaling of multifunctional food hubs requires indicators that capture **reach, sustainability, and community impact**.

Quantitative measures include participant numbers, attendance, vendor participation, and income diversification.

Qualitative indicators should assess community ownership, partnership strength, integration of social and commercial activities, and improvements in food access, health, and social cohesion.

A mixed-methods approach is essential, combining surveys, interviews, observation, and digital data tools to capture both performance and lived experience. These methods are complementary and can reveal crucial insights that singular methods can omit.

Evaluation should be guided by a clear theory of change and focus on operational sustainability and community impact. Participatory evaluation is crucial, ensuring communities help define success and support continuous learning and improvement.

Overview of key upscaling steps

Address key barriers

- Simplify and align regulatory frameworks across food, health, and community sectors.
- Strengthen municipal and community support mechanisms.
- Improve infrastructure and ensure consistent demand.
- Balance financial sustainability with social accessibility.

Secure municipal support

- Advocate for enabling regulatory frameworks tailored to multifunctional markets.
- Seek municipal financial contributions or co-investment where appropriate.
- Build long-term partnerships with local producers.
- Co-create initiatives with communities to ensure demand and relevance.

Adapt to external conditions

- Develop strategies to remain resilient in times of economic or geopolitical uncertainty (e.g., inflation, war impacts).

Diversify funding streams

- Combine public grants, private sector partnerships, and earned revenue
- Use hybrid models to blend commercial activities with social mission funding.

Build strong operational foundations

- Develop a motivated, adaptable, and skilled market team with both entrepreneurial and community development expertise.
- Establish governance structures that ensure accountability to both financial and social objectives.

Strengthen producer and community relationships

- Build long-term partnerships with local producers.
- Co-create initiatives with communities to ensure demand and relevance.

Promote cooperation between markets

- Establish or join a market association to share knowledge, resources, and advocacy.
- Foster peer-to-peer learning between market teams at local, regional, and national levels.